

MODERN METHODS AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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***Abstract.** The necessary information on the rational use of modern innovative technologies and the use of proven teaching methods in teaching English, one of the world's languages, is currently being presented. In this article, modern and tried-and-tested methods of teaching English and necessary tips for new learners to learn English quickly and easily are given.*

***Keywords:** language, english, independent language learning, modern technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.*

INTRODUCTION

By the end of the 20th century, English had finally established itself as a world language. Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and later at institutes, training courses or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Popular methods of teaching and learning English and Internet resources were used in the research process. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

MAIN PART

After the independence of our country, the interest of young people in learning foreign languages increased, and many opportunities for language learning are created by our country. As our first president Islam Karimov said: At present, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not in vain.

Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of mastering foreign languages for our country, which is striving to take its rightful place in the world community, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners." Especially in primary education. One of the decisions that led to positive changes is the Decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" dated December 10, 2012 PQ-1875. to teach languages, mainly English, to further increase their interest in teaching foreign languages, to teach English classes in all educational institutions with various innovative methods, and at the same time to improve students' oral speech development, transition of teaching grammar through modern, innovative methods began step by step.

Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing. This is because it is becoming more and more difficult to live without knowing English in the course of life. But

language learning also depends on age. Scientists have even proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, the fact that children have more time than adults, and they keep the learned information in their memory quickly.

Here are the basic and necessary tips for learning English quickly and effectively:

1. Define the goal clearly

Without a clear goal, it is impossible to achieve success in any work, especially in language learning. Therefore, think about what you want to learn English for. When I was a student, after studying, I taught English at a private language teaching center. The first lesson is always "Why do you want to study English?" I would start with a question. Unfortunately, more than half of the class could not say the exact purpose. There were many people who simply said, "My parents are sending it, it will be useful." Since learning a language is a long and arduous process, a person who embarks on this path without a clear goal will never learn a language. On the contrary, the more serious your goal is, the faster and more effective language learning will be.

Everyone can set the goal based on their circumstances. For example, a school student can set a goal: "In two years, I will study English and enter the University of Westminster on a grant basis." A student may intend to "prepare for the TOEFL and enter an American university to study for a master's degree on the basis of a grant." A businessman can set a goal: "By learning English, I will learn new know-how related to my business and bring my company to the world market in 5 years." Do not forget that the more serious the goal, the faster and more effective language learning will be.

2. Language is based on repetition

A language cannot be learned without constant repetition. You can memorize 10 new words a day, but if you don't repeat these words after 1-2 days, you will definitely forget them. One of the most effective ways is flash cards. Or, if not, you can effectively use the most eye-catching places. Personally, I used to write down the words I learned on a small piece of paper and stick them around my computer monitor and on my bedside table.

3. Communicate

Language is a means of communication. Therefore, in order to learn and develop a language, you naturally need to communicate. When I was a student, there were Speaking Clubs in various libraries and resource centers. Don't be afraid to participate even if you are not fluent yet. The one who tries to speak, even if he does not know the language better, wins than the one who is shy to participate in such conversations despite knowing the language. So, don't be shy, speak even with mistakes.

Or, if not, find a partner to practice your English further. Another advantage of learning a language with one or more partners is that this method creates a unique competitive environment between partners. A neighbor or a classmate at school can be your partner. If you agree to learn at least 30 new words every week and meet on Sunday to test each other, you will definitely try to memorize the words so as not to fall behind your partner.

4. Adapt the language learning process to your lifestyle

Adapt the process of learning English to your lifestyle. For example, if you go to the university by subway every day, you will spend at least 30-40 minutes a day in the subway (counting 15-20 minutes each way). So, to make the most of your time on the subway, you can

listen to various Listening Comprehension exercises (for example, Investudy English podcasts). Otherwise, when I was a student, classes were often canceled. This meant that I had to wait at least 1 hour for the next lesson. If you have similar situations, you can go to the library and spend this time only on things related to the English language. Otherwise, there is probably no one who does not watch movies of various genres. If you want to watch a movie, watch it in English with subtitles.

5. Use your smartphone effectively

Since learning a language is a long and arduous process, you should try to make it as easy as possible. Your smartphone will come in handy. There are free English learning programs that can be installed on smartphones. The most popular among them are Duolingo and Memrise. Duolingo and Memrise are similar. But the first noticeable difference is that in Duolingo, words are pronounced more in American English, and in Memrise in British English. Someone who knows a little English can listen to TED talks. After installing TED on your smartphone, you can listen to the conversation with subtitles if you select English subtitles in the Settings section.

Learning English is not easy. This requires you to set a clear goal, keep repeating new words, communicate without shame when you have the opportunity, adapt the process of learning English to your life, and finally, use technology effectively. Grammar in English For a beginner, it can seem overwhelming. Articles, pronouns, verbs - there are many rules in English that are not easy to translate into Russian. This raises doubts, but is it worth starting at all? Is it worth diving into if you're not sure you can master English grammar? No, you won't get far in your studies with that attitude. Therefore, it is important to abandon all doubts and stereotypes. Believe me, you can learn English grammar by yourself and in the shortest possible time. All that is required of you is persistence and determination, and we will help you with everything else.

At first glance, English grammar may seem like the most difficult set of rules to learn. But, believe me, the real truth is not like that! As difficult, confusing and boring as English grammar may seem, it can become one of the simplest and easiest things in the world for you to learn in seconds. Only your desire is enough for this!

The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required during the course of foreign language classes. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many

organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in training sessions. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and will be educated.

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